

ISic3582

Monumental fragment reading NSVM

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2019-07-16 - Jonathan Prag edited the file based on autopsy and study for 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated in 1971, in room 7 of the west portico of the agora

Coordinates

37.997856, 14.262463

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory 30592

Physical Description

Two joining fragments of thin coarse yellow-white marble. Height 28-28.3 cm; width (max) 27 cm; depth 2cm (top) to 2.8 cm (base, excluding moulding). The upper and lower margins are intact on both fragments; both are broken to left and right. A simple raised moulding (damaged) survives along the lower edge of both fragments.

Dimensions

Height 28-28.3 cm

Width 27 cm

Depth 2-2.8 cm

Layout

A single line of large Latin letters is preserved on the face

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are relatively thinly and shallowly V-cut with a fairly smooth finish to the strokes, tall and closely spaced. The first hasta of the M slopes off vertical.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 155-165 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: N/A mm

Text

1. [---]nsum[---]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation

Commentary

The break on the left follows the line of a slanting stroke, and the fact that the M later in the text has an initial sloping hasta demonstrates that this must be N, not M. The stroke visible just above the letter at the left margin is later damage and not a letter stroke. The final stroke of the M is lost. The most likely possibilities for this combination of letters in such a monumental text are consummare (common in describing completion of an undertaking or building) and consumere (common in describing a building damaged / destroyed and now replaced / rebuilt); mensum and censum might also be possible.

The text belongs to the first, second, or earlier third century AD.

The fragments have some similarity to ISic3580 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3580>] and ISic3581 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3581>], but they should be treated separately for a number of reasons: the letter forms are distinct in their style (narrower, shallower, with finer serifs, and rounded at the junction of two upright strokes, as in V and M, which is also off-vertical here but vertical in the other two), the type of stone is not identical, and the form of the stone is different in both thickness and the moulding at the lower edge.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645653

Bibliography

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. *Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.12

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